

Title: Making smart contracts even smarter

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INTRODUCTION:

AI in Blockchain -- Making smart contracts even smarter. Smart contracts enables business logic on top of the blockchain as a database. Smart contracts are deterministic and that's why business logic is mostly hard coded in the smart contracts. AI is probabilistic, and that's why not a natural fit for the smart contract. However, the training can happen outside of the contract, and every model improvements can be hard coded to blockchain. This is one way to make blockchains smarter. In this talk, we are going to explore more ways to explore AI & Blockchain integration.

AIM:

to explore ways AI and Blockchain work together to build smart consensus system.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This talk is a commentary on the current status of blockchain & AI. We do not require to run any experiments.

RESULTS:

This talk is a commentary on the current status of blockchain & AI. We do not require to run any experiments.

CONCLUSIONS:

AI & Blockchain combined can create new business models using various consensus and distribution models.

KEYWORDS:

AI; Blockchain; Smart Contracts;

BIOGRAPHY:

Chinmay is a tech leader, public speaker, and a serial entrepreneur. He has a decade of team building and product development experience. He is currently the founder and CEO of BlockX Labs. He works with his clients to help them explore the full potential of blockchain technologies and build strategies to apply blockchain to solve their current pain points. His aim is to bring mature software development and sound product design strategies to the world of blockchain software development.